

CALL FOR PAPERS

Rethinking Operations and Supply Chains Management in Contemporary Challenges

IMPORTANT DEADLINES

- Submission of Full Paper: until September 30, 2026
- Initial decision sent to authors: until November 30, 2026
- Deadline for revised papers: January 30, 2027
- Notification of acceptance: until March 30, 2027
- Deadline for final versions: April 30, 2027

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MAIN TOPIC

This special issue seeks to broaden and consolidate the contribution of Operations and Supply Chain Management (OSCM) research in the *Brazilian Administration Review (BAR)*, fostering debate within OSCM communities in emerging economies while remaining connected to international discussions in the field. We welcome studies that examine how operations and supply chains are organized, coordinated, and transformed in practice, especially in contexts marked by uncertainty, institutional complexity, diversity, and structural constraints common to emerging economies. Submissions may explore topics such as operational and supply chain resilience, innovation, risk management, sustainability, digitalization, public-private interactions, industrial and service operations, inter-organizational relationships, illicit practices and crime, diversity, among other topics. Overall, the special issue aims to foster research that is relevant to both scholars and practitioners concerned with contemporary operational challenges.

AIMS AND SCOPE

Over the past decades, the OSCM literature has advanced understanding of how firms manage operations and inter-organizational flows of materials and information (Roehrich et al., 2025). OSCM research has traditionally examined a wide range of phenomena, including performance (Wu et al., 2010), supply chain integration (Flynn et al., 2016), and resilience under uncertainty and risk (Azadegan & Dooley, 2021; Freitas et al., 2024; Queiroz et al., 2024). In this special issue, OSCM is understood as a field that spans operational decision-making within firms and across networks, encompassing manufacturing and services, private and public organizations, and local as well as global supply chains.

A growing body of research has demonstrated the relevance of OSCM to contemporary challenges such as pandemics (Lusiantoro & Pradiptyo, 2022; Shen & Sun, 2023), sustainability (Silva et al., 2023; Wieland & Durach, 2021), digital transformation (Caiado et al., 2021), and increasing exposure to institutional and geopolitical uncertainties (Bednarski et al., 2025; Freitas et al., 2025). Despite these advances, important questions remain insufficiently explored, particularly in contexts characterized by institutional complexity, infrastructural constraints, and social inequality (Freitas et al., 2025; Paiva et al., 2024), features that are salient in emerging economies. This special issue seeks to address these gaps by encouraging contributions that advance understanding of OSCM phenomena and their managerial and societal implications. Topics of interest include, but are not limited to:

Theoretical developments in OSCM

- Agrifood supply chains
- Crime and illicit practices in OSCM
- Digital technologies and data-driven decision-making in operations and supply chains
- Diversity, equity, and inclusion in OSCM
- Governance, power, and coordination in supply chain relationships
- Human rights, justice, and forced labor
- Leadership in OSCM
- Methodological innovations in OSCM research
- Operations and supply chain resilience, risk, and uncertainty management
- Operations and supply chains in emerging and developing economies
- Public-private interactions and operations in regulated or high-risk environments
- Public and private purchasing
- Sustainability, circular economy, and responsible operations
- The role of operations and supply chains in industrial development and competitiveness

SUBMISSION PROCESS

Authors are encouraged to submit original manuscripts that follow BAR's submission guidelines by **September 30, 2026**, using the journal's **ScholarOne system**. At the first stage of submission, **'SI Operations and Supply Chains'** must be selected as the **manuscript type**. Papers may be written in **English, Portuguese, or Spanish**. However, if a manuscript submitted in Portuguese or Spanish is accepted, authors will be required to provide a full English version, ensuring both linguistic quality and consistency with the original text. Given BAR's international approach, **all accepted articles are published in English**.

By submitting a manuscript, authors confirm that the work is original, has not been published previously, and is not under consideration by another journal, in whole or in part. Submissions must also comply with BAR's policies on plagiarism and self-plagiarism. All manuscripts are first assessed by the Guest Editors and the Editor-in-Chief. Those considered suitable are then assigned to associate editors and reviewers from BAR's editorial boards for double-blind peer review. Acceptance depends on the authors' ability to address the comments and suggestions provided by reviewers and editors.

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ABOUT THE BRAZILIAN ADMINISTRATION REVIEW (BAR)

Launched in 2004 by the Brazilian Academy of Management (ANPAD), BAR has an international scope in terms of topics of interest, target audience, and editorial boards. It is an A2 journal according to the Brazilian classification Qualis/Capes (second highest rank), which is evidence of the quality of published works and the transparency of the editorial process. BAR follows the editorial principles available in the document Best Practices in Scientific Publication, an initiative by the Brazilian Academy of Management (ANPAD) to assist journals in meeting high scholarly standards and enhancing their theoretical and applied impact. BAR is also a member of COPE (Committee on Publication Ethics) and a signatory of DORA (San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment), which is additional evidence of BAR's commitment to the most rigorous ethical principles in scholarly publication.

BAR publishes documents within the interests of business and public administration, management science, and organization studies. Diverse theoretical and methodological perspectives are welcome as long as they contribute to advancing the frontiers of a specific theoretical tradition and are also insightful to practice. Prospective authors should note that studies with blurred boundaries between what is inherent to organization studies and what may be framed within the interests of, for instance, anthropology and sociology will be rejected. Symptomatically, a large body of research has been misleading organization scholars. The same policy applies to studies that are not fully characterized within another scholarly field but whose main interests concern isolated issues, such as culture, gender, race, performance, impact, and the like. BAR's editorial scope for research articles does not include teaching cases, theoretical essays, opinion papers, purely applied practitioner-oriented technical material, and replication studies. As for the latter, replication is here conceived in broad terms, including the testing of theories (confirmation/refutation of previous findings), contextualization studies (application of scales to a different context), and perspective studies (collection of data from a different demographic group). Systematic literature reviews will be considered only if they address issues of contemporary interest both for theory development and application in organizations.

BAR is aligned with Open Science practices: data, materials and open codes, in addition to the dissemination of additional information related to the editorial process. The journal is a member and subscribes to the principles of COPE - Committee for Ethics in Publications.

BAR is present in many of the most prestigious indexing platforms, such as WOS, Scopus, SciELO, Spell, Cabell's, ProQuest, DOAJ, EBSCO, Gale/Cengage Learning, IBSS, Latindex, Ullrichs, and Redalyc.

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